

Opportunity costs of rewetting agriculturally used organic soils in Germany

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ABSTRACT

Rewetting organic soils used in agriculture to lower GHG emissions makes current land use practices impossible, leading to costs that go beyond the technical aspects of rewetting. Farmers have to forgo the profits that could be achieved with the drained use of organic soils. We estimate these costs at the municipal level based on a crop-type map generated using remote sensing technologies, combined with short-term standard gross margins and long-term tenure fees. We estimate the maximum of average short-term opportunity costs of rewetting one hectare of organic soil to range from €674 in Brandenburg to €2726 in Lower Saxony. Relating the maximum short-term opportunity costs to the GHG mitigation potential of rewetting organic soils yields mitigation costs ranging from €24 to €91 per t CO₂eq among federal states. This is substantially below the estimated economic welfare losses of €237 per ton of CO₂ emitted (UBA, 2023), even if additional costs of rewetting, such as engineering and management costs, are accounted for. Recently introduced federal state-specific interventions for peatland protection measures under the second pillar of the “Common Agricultural Policy” (CAP) can cover the average short-term opportunity costs of rewetting if combined with other CAP second pillar interventions. However, the interventions do not capture the high variability in opportunity costs across a federal state and have a reliable time horizon of only 7 years. Our results can inform the design of region- and farm-type-specific compensation measures to make rewetting attractive to farmers. Furthermore, they are relevant for a cost-benefit analysis of rewetting agriculturally used organic soils. Finally, they can inform debates on rewetting organic soils in other EU member states.

1. Introduction

Peatlands cover 3–4% of the global land area (Olsson et al., 2019). Due to drainage, approximately 12% of this area is no longer naturally water-saturated (UNEP, 2022). Whenever peatlands are drained, the soil organic carbon decomposes (Tapio-Biström et al., 2012), resulting in carbon dioxide emissions that account for approximately 5% of total global greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions.

In Germany, approximately 1.3 million hectares of agricultural land are located on drained organic soil (Tiemeyer et al., 2020). Although this accounts for only 7% of total agricultural land (DESTATIS, 2022), it is responsible for more than 40% of total GHG emissions from agriculture and agricultural land use (UBA, 2023). Therefore, halting carbon decomposition processes by rewetting them has become a prominent focus in scientific and political discourse on reducing agricultural GHG emissions.

Many farmers and other stakeholders relying on the drained use of organic soils have a critical perspective on rewetting organic soils (Buschmann et al., 2020; Petrick et al., 2025). Reasons for this include the high costs and the irreversibility of rewetting, as well as the uncertainty about the feasibility and economic viability of wet land use alternatives such as paludiculture (Latacz-Lohmann et al., 2019). Farmers fear losing their farms or, at the very least, expect a deterioration in their current income situation. In order to gain political support for rewetting from stakeholders relying on the drained use of organic soils, wet use business cases need to be developed, turning rewetting into an economic opportunity. Otherwise, land users and owners have few incentives to move away from considering rewetting as a threat.

As the rewetting of organic soils only aims at raising the water table to the soil surface and not necessarily at restoring natural peatland conditions (IPCC, 2014), there are two economically promising types of wet land use alternatives. First, paludiculture, a peat-conserving

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cultivation of plants adapted to wet conditions (Wichtmann and Joosten, 2007). Second, photovoltaic plants on rewetted peatlands (Fakharizadehshirazi and Rösch, 2023). Theoretically, either the profits from producing biomass in paludiculture or the profits from generating energy with photovoltaic plants have the potential to compensate for the economic losses associated with the termination of drainage-based land use activities (Böhm et al., 2022). However, neither paludiculture nor the installation of photovoltaic plants on rewetted peatlands has been implemented on a large scale yet.

As wet value chains are not yet developed at scale, the compensation of farmers' income losses from terminating drainage-based land use activities is essential in the short- to medium-term (Grethe et al., 2021; Herold et al., 2025). Estimating these income losses, which can be denoted as the agricultural opportunity cost of rewetting, is an important basis for developing governance approaches for rewetting agricultural peatlands that result in a fair distribution of the costs of rewetting.

Such governance approaches include financial transfers through private (Nordt et al., 2022) or public (Agora Agriculture, 2024) and (Agora Agriculture, 2026) carbon markets, as well as rewetting premiums under the Common Agricultural Policy of the EU (CAP) or national programmes such as under the German Action Program for Natural Climate Protection (ANK) (BMUV, 2023).

The largest public agricultural funding instrument in the European Union is the CAP (Regulation (EU) 2021/2115). Interventions to compensate for income losses resulting from the rewetting of organic soils are implemented under the second pillar of the CAP (EL-0101-03/04). Such payments are often accompanied by one-off payments covering initial investment costs (Pabst et al., 2018). In addition to the second pillar interventions of the CAP, the "European Regional Development Fund" is used to cofinance investments in peatland protection measures. In the coming years, the German ANK is likely to become the most important national instrument to finance peatland rewetting, with a budget of 680 million € being foreseen for the period until 2028 (Herold et al., 2025).

Whatever the funding mechanism, determining appropriate levels of income compensation requires knowledge of the opportunity costs of rewetting and, thus, of the current use and profitability of drained organic soils. Abandoning drainage-based land use on organic soils affects directly marketed crops (e.g., wheat) and forage crops (grassland, silage maize), predominantly used to feed the farm's livestock. Farmers are forced to reduce the number of ruminants kept if losses in forage areas cannot be compensated by expanding roughage production elsewhere (Schaller, 2015). This is particularly the case in regions with a high share of organic soils in the total agricultural area (Krimly et al., 2016). Consequently, the opportunity costs of forage areas are related to the income generated with ruminants dependent on the roughage from the rewetted area, while the opportunity costs of land cultivated with marketable crops solely depend on the income generated with these crops.

Shortly after rewetting and thus after abandoning drainage-based land use activities, the opportunity costs exceed the foregone income. This is because not all cost components can be eliminated immediately (Röder and Osterburg, 2010). Fixed costs (e.g., machinery, employees, buildings) do not directly depend on the scope and intensity of production processes. They cannot be eliminated immediately after discontinuation of a production process (Dabbert and Braun, 2021). The foregone gross margins (revenues minus variable costs) can be taken as an indicator of the short-term opportunity costs. In contrast, the foregone profits (revenues minus all costs, including family-owned labor and capital, which may be used in other activities) indicate the long-term opportunity costs of rewetting organic soils. We use current tenure fees as a proxy for these profits.

This study aims to enhance the understanding of how peatlands are utilized in agriculture and to quantify the opportunity costs of rewetting farmed organic soils across the municipality, county, and federal state levels in Germany. Our analysis builds on previous studies that

determined opportunity costs based on data with lower spatial resolution (Koppensteiner et al., 2023; Röder and Grützmacher, 2012; Röder and Osterburg, 2010) or only for selected regions in Germany (Krimly et al., 2016; Schaller, 2015). Our results inform political discourse on appropriate levels of income compensation that incentivize farmers to rewet their land. We discuss our results in the context of a broader cost-benefit perspective of rewetting, current rewetting policies, and political implications.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Research area

We analyze all agriculturally used and thus 73% of organic soils according to the German definition (Tiemeyer et al., 2020). Organic soils consist of the soil types peatland (soil organic matter $\geq 30\%$, thickness ≥ 30 cm) and peaty soil (soil organic matter (dry mass) $\geq 15\%$, thickness 10–40 cm). Tegetmeyer et al. (2021) provided a map according to this definition of organic soils for the entire country of Germany (hereafter referred to as the *organic soil map*). Non-agricultural land use categories, such as forests, shrublands, and settlements, are excluded from this analysis.

2.2. Land use analysis

Estimating the opportunity costs of rewetting organic soils requires detailed knowledge of their current use, as the profitability depends on the land use to be abandoned. The site-specific identification of land use has been a major obstacle in the past (Koppensteiner et al., 2023; Wichtmann et al., 2022a). The available data either has a limited differentiation of land use types, a low spatial resolution, i.e., at the county level, or is difficult to access, such as the Integrated Administration and Control System, due to strict data protection requirements (Laggner et al., 2014).

To overcome these limitations, we used the parcel-based crop type map generated by Tetteh et al. (2024). The parcel-based crop map per year is created in three stages. First, a pixel-based crop type map containing 24 crop types is created based on the approach of Blickensdörfer et al. (2022). Second, agricultural parcel boundaries per year are delineated using the methods of Tetteh et al. (2021, 2023). Finally, the agricultural parcels are spatially overlaid on the pixel-based map per year, and the crop type of each parcel is assigned based on majority voting, resulting in a *parcel-based vector crop type map* (hereafter referred to as the *crop type map*) per year. Our analysis is carried out using crop-type maps for 2021, 2022, and 2023 to account for annual variability in cropping patterns and price and cost changes, with map accuracies around 85%. This analysis is enabled by the high-resolution remote sensing data, which has overlapped with numerous statistical surveys, such as those on animal populations and land use, since 2020.

In addition to analyzing cultivated crop types, ruminant husbandry is highly dependent on regional forage areas and is therefore included in the analysis. The *crop type map* from remote sensing cannot provide information about livestock densities, nor distinguish between corn and silage maize. Information to estimate these parameters is taken from the Thünen Agricultural Atlas by Neuenfeldt et al. (2024). They provide consistent estimates of land use and livestock densities at the municipal level. The dataset creates a harmonized, comprehensive and publicly available dataset on German agricultural statistics at the municipality level, from 1999 to the present. To achieve this, it integrates data from various sources, including the German Farm Structure Survey (FSS), official agricultural statistics, and geo-referenced land use information of the Coordination of Information on the Environment (CORINE), using Bayesian estimation and cluster analysis, while ensuring data security requirements are met (Gocht and Röder, 2014; Röder and Gocht, 2013). When estimating the number of ruminants dependent on forage from organic soils, information on the share of silage maize used as a forage

Table 1
Crop type aggregations.

Main Crop Group	Crop Type	Productive agricultural area incl. special crops	Productive agricultural area excl. special crops	Productive arable land excl. special crops
Permanent Grassland	Permanent grassland	X	X	
Arable forage crops	Cultivated grassland, Silage maize (Forage / Biogas)	X	X	X
Cereals	Cereal maize, Wheat, Rye, Barley, Oat	X	X	X
Oil crops	Rapeseed, Sunflower	X	X	X
Root Crops	Potato, Sugar beet	X	X	X
Legumes	Grain legumes	X	X	X
Special Crops	Vegetables, Hops, Orchard, Grapevine	X		
Unproductive agricultural areas	Fallow land, Small woody features			

Source: Own composition, based on crop types of [Tetteh et al., \(2024\)](#), and [Neuenfeldt et al., \(2024\)](#). Remark: Crop types marked with an X are included in the corresponding aggregation. The crop type aggregations are based on the classification of land use categories, which is exemplary and used to distinguish the subsidy levels for organic farming ([BLE, 2023](#)).

crop and as a fermentation substrate for biogas plants is required. This information is taken from the “German Maize Committee,” which annually commissions surveys (ca. 2000 surveyed farms) to estimate the shares of biogas and forage maize at the federal-state level (KYNETEC, o. J.).

The *organic soil map*, the *crop type map*, and the consistent estimates of land use and livestock densities at the municipality level are processed in R¹ and Python. This produces a dataset containing information on the crop type cultivated on each parcel on organic soils, along with the municipality in which each parcel is located. Each parcel or field indicated by the *crop type map* as being cultivated with maize is divided by the municipality-specific share of silage and cereal maize given in [Neuenfeldt et al. \(2024\)](#). The fraction of silage maize is further divided based on its intended use, considering the federal and state-specific shares of biogas and forage maize obtained (KYNETEC, o. J.).

The average net energy yield of the different forage crops is considered when allocating the number of ruminants kept in a municipality to its forage area. For this purpose, the total net energy yield of all forage areas within a municipality is determined by multiplying the area of each forage crop type by the corresponding average net energy yield per hectare ([Dilger and Faulhaber, 2006a](#)). We have regionalized permanent grassland yields and, hence, net energy density for calculating the upper value of short-term opportunity costs (SOC) over the years. To do this, we combined moving event maps from remote sensing ([Schwieder et al., 2022](#)) with average yields to better map yield distribution at the district level. The field-collected events were aggregated at the district level, and an estimation model was used to ensure that the yields at the NUTS 2 level from Standard Gross Margins (SGM) remain the same when aggregated (weighted) across districts (for more information, see Appendix 1).

¹ All data, shape files and calculation routines are stored in a repository and can be downloaded on request.

Subsequently, the total number of ruminants, categorized by ruminant type, kept within the municipality is divided by the total net energy yield. The result is a municipality-specific number of ruminants, categorized by ruminant type, fed with one energy unit. This number is multiplied by the net energy yield of each forage parcel located on organic soils. It provides the number of ruminants, categorized by ruminant type, based on the amount of roughage from the parcel. The number of animals is multiplied by the livestock units per ruminant to gain information on the ruminant's density. The land-use data obtained at the parcel level is aggregated to higher levels, namely the county and the state. A detailed calculation is provided in Appendix 2.

2.3. Short-term opportunity cost analysis²

The short-term opportunity costs of abandoning drainage-based land use activities on organic soils are determined based on the land use data generated at the municipality level as described in [Section 2.2](#) and the crop type and ruminant type-specific standard gross margins published by [KTBL \(2023\)](#) at the administrative district level for the years 2021, 2022, and 2023. The standard gross margins are nationwide and consistently determined according to the official methodology for farm typology of the European Commission ([COMMISSION DECISION of 7 June, 1985 Establishing a Community Typology for Agricultural Holdings 85/377/EEC, 1985; Sauer and Hardeweg, 2019](#)). To obtain average values and standard deviations, we calculate the short-term opportunity cost for each year 2021, 2022, and 2023, and calculate the average over all three years to reduce the influence of volatile revenues and factor costs ([Blanck and Bahrs, 2009](#)), but get an estimate on the variance over time. Standard gross margins are revenues free of variable special costs (direct costs) but not variable work completion costs ([Sauer and Hardeweg, 2019](#)). According to economic theory, variable costs associated with work completion can be quickly eliminated following the cessation of the production process. The obstacle of variable work completion costs is that they vary widely, even between farms in the same region. For this reason, nationwide analyses such as the one presented here and those of ([Koppensteiner et al., 2023](#)) are based on standard gross margins. However, they lead to a slight overestimation of the opportunity costs.

Standard gross margins are based on product-related revenues and exclude decoupled subsidies. This is in line with the recent CAP regulation, whereby organic soils retain their general subsidy eligibility if they are rewetted and used with wet land use alternatives ([Regulation \(EU\) 2021/2115](#)).

The short-term opportunity costs of rewetting a parcel previously cultivated with a certain crop type equal the standard gross margin that could be earned with this crop type. Consequently, the average short-term opportunity costs of rewetting are a weighted combination of all the standard gross margins corresponding to the crops that are to be abandoned. This approach neglects the possibility of farms adjusting their production program, but avoids the need for farm individual data ([Krimly et al., 2016](#)).

To account for the different degrees to which ruminant husbandry may be affected by rewetting, a range of short-term opportunity costs is given. The lower boundary of short-term opportunity costs assumes that the rewetting of forage areas has no impact on ruminant husbandry, as forage can be sourced from alternative land. Forage areas are treated as surplus forage areas. The standard gross margins for surplus forage areas, as provided by [KTBL \(2023\)](#), are applied. The upper boundary assumes that losses in the forage area cannot be compensated at all by other forage. In this case, the short-term opportunity costs of a forage area equal the sum of the standard gross margins that could be earned with the ruminants assigned to that area ([Schaller, 2015](#)).

Due to the distinct characteristics of crops cultivated on organic soils,

² Formulas for calculating opportunity costs are provided in Appendix 2.

Fig. 1. Land use categories on agriculturally used organic soils. Source: Own illustration and calculations based on Tetteh et al. (2024) and Tegetmeyer et al. (2021).

Fig. 2. Arable forage crops and main crop groups of arable land on organic soils. Source: Own illustration and calculations.

the analysis identifies *crop type aggregations*. All aggregations focus on productive agricultural crop types and either include or exclude the leading crop group of special crops, as the standard gross margins of these crops significantly deviate from those of the others. In addition to the crop type aggregations presented in Table 1, permanent grassland is analyzed separately because it is a land-use category. The average short-term opportunity costs calculated at the municipality level, including both lower and upper bounds for each crop type group, are combined to the county and higher regional levels.

2.4. Long-term opportunity cost analysis

The long-term opportunity costs of rewetting agriculturally used organic soils are estimated based on the tenure fees provided by (DESTATIS, 2021) for the year 2020. This follows the approach of (Röder and Osterburg, 2010) and (Schaller, 2015), who also distinguish the tenure fees by the land use categories, such as arable land, permanent grassland, and other agricultural areas at the federal-state level. A higher spatial resolution and a more recent dataset that distinguishes between land-use categories is not available for all federal states. The

tenure fees are weighted based on each land use category's share in the total productive agriculturally used area on organic soils at the municipality level. The category of special crops is assigned to the tenure fees for other agricultural regions.

Using tenure fees as a proxy for long-term opportunity costs of rewetting may over- or underestimate real opportunity costs for several reasons. First, land purchasing prices often exceed capitalized tenure fees if market interest rates are used. This reflects option values of agricultural land (later use e.g. for construction), as well as options for non-agricultural uses of land (renewable energy, nature conservation measures, storing wealth). Some of these non-agricultural uses are likely to be available also on rewetted land in the future, e.g. solar power and nature conservation measures, others may not (use for construction, use for balancing livestock numbers with area endowment). Second, in the long-term wet use options for agriculture will materialize, e.g. through the development of paludiculture value chains for replacing fossil-based materials in the bioeconomy, and will thus lower the income foregone due to rewetting. All these factors are uncertain and strongly depend on political framework conditions extending beyond agricultural policies. We therefore consider current tenure fees as the best proxy for long-term

Fig. 3. Ruminant livestock density on real forage area located on organic soils (2021–2023 average). Source: Own illustration and calculations based on KYNETEC, unpublished; Tegetmeyer et al. (2021); 4 Neuenfeldt et al. (2024); Tetteh et al. (2024).

Table 2
Three-year (2021–2023) average opportunity costs of rewetting agriculturally used organic soils.

Average opportunity costs in €/ha*a	Short-term						Long-term
	Productive agricultural area incl. special crops		Productive arable land excl. special crops		Permanent grassland		Productive agricultural area incl. special crops
	lower boundary	upper boundary	lower boundary	upper boundary	lower boundary	upper boundary	
Schleswig-Holstein	514 (119)	2567 (633)	891 (203)	2430 (534)	377 (147)	2541 (746)	356 (9.83)
Lower Saxony	741 (323)	2726 (939)	972 (358)	2428 (644)	227 (86)	2604 (1034)	431 (2.39)
Bavaria	1021 (1337)	2348 (1308)	1203 (390)	2105 (652)	507 (175)	2152 (756)	346 (3.3)
Brandenburg	263 (103)	674 (165)	460 (131)	862 (138)	118 (60)	533 (187)	146 (0.42)
M-Western Pomerania	289 (323)	813 (466)	937 (526)	1431 (451)	136 (72)	666 (279)	190 (1.00)
Germany average	598 (1086)	1959 (1231)	902 (410)	2027 (734)	232 (193)	1713 (845)	318 (3.11)

Source: Own calculations. Remark: Data land use: 2021–2023, data standard gross margins: 2021–2023 (standard deviation in brackets), data tenure fees: 2020.

opportunity costs in this study.

3. Results

3.1. Agricultural land use of organic soils

Organic soils are unequally distributed among the German federal states. Almost 90% of the organic soils are located in five out of 16 federal states: Lower Saxony (40% of total agriculturally used organic soils), Mecklenburg-Western Pomerania (15%), Brandenburg (14%), Schleswig-Holstein (10%), and Bavaria (9%).

Agriculturally used organic soils can be divided into five land use categories (Fig. 1). Permanent grassland covers two-thirds of the productive agricultural area (three-year average 759,718 ha). Arable land (351,926 ha) and special crops (6683 ha) account for the other third. Land use on organic soils thus contrasts with total agricultural land use in Germany, where permanent grassland accounts for about 29% and arable land accounts for 68%. The most significant deviation between the cultivation of organic soils and mineral soils can be observed in Mecklenburg-Western Pomerania. Permanent grassland accounts for 62% of the agriculturally productive organic soils but only 20% of all

agricultural soils. Bavaria and Lower Saxony are the federal states The highest shares of arable land in agriculturally productive organic soils are found in Bavaria (36%) and Lower Saxony (35%).

In addition to the large proportion of permanent grassland used for roughage production, also arable land on organic soils is predominantly used to cultivate arable forage crops (54%, Fig. 2). Cereals cover the second-largest share of arable land located on organic soils (33%). The remaining 13% is split between root crops (5%), oil crops (6%), and grain legumes (2%).

In Fig. 2, the main crop group of arable forage crops is divided by its crop types and by the use of silage maize. This differentiation allows the exclusion of the silage maize cultivated for biogas production from the forage area used to produce roughage for ruminant husbandry (real forage area: permanent grassland, cultivated grassland, silage maize (forage)).

3.2. Ruminant Husbandry on Organic Soils

Forage crops (excl. biogas maize) are cultivated on 80% of all agriculturally used organic soils in Germany. Approximately 13% of all ruminants in Germany are fed on roughage from organic soils. Lower

Fig. 4. Distribution of SOC at the county level, lower and upper boundary by different land classes. Source: Own calculations. Remark: Land use data: 2021–2023; gross margins data: 2021–2023. The bar chart below the main four charts, in the first row, shows the area of organic soils for the upper boundary, and the second row of bar charts shows the areas for the lower boundary.

Saxony is the federal state with the most ruminants dependent on roughage from organic soils and with the highest ruminant livestock density per hectare of real forage area on organic soils (1.83 LU/ha, Fig. 3). Similar livestock densities can be observed in Schleswig-Holstein and Bavaria. Low livestock densities and a high share of suckler cows characterize ruminant husbandry on organic soils in Brandenburg and Mecklenburg-Western Pomerania.

3.3. Average Opportunity Costs of Rewetting Agriculturally Used Organic Soils

The average three-year short-term opportunity costs vary between 118 and 2726 €/ha*a (Table 2). Within the same region, rewetting permanent grassland typically results in lower short-term opportunity costs than rewetting arable land. This is due to low market prices paid for surplus roughage (KTBL, 2023) and lower livestock densities compared to arable forage areas. Furthermore, certain marketable crops (e.g., potatoes) generate higher standard gross margins per hectare than ruminant husbandry. In the German average, the short-term opportunity costs (upper boundary) of rewetting a hectare of arable land amount to 2027 €/ha*a (excluding speciality crops). This exceeds the short-term opportunity costs of rewetting permanent grassland with 1713 €/ha*a.

Regardless of the crop type considered, the average short-term opportunity costs for Schleswig-Holstein, Lower Saxony, and Bavaria are substantially higher than those for Brandenburg and Mecklenburg-Western Pomerania. One reason is the higher density of ruminant livestock. Furthermore, dairy cows generating high standard gross margins are the dominant ruminant type. Another reason is the generally higher soil productivity of land in the western and southern federal states, which is reflected by higher standard gross margins per crop type as well as higher tenure fees.

Larger proportions of arable crop types with high standard gross margins (potatoes, wheat, cereal maize) are the reason for higher short-term opportunity costs (lower boundary) of rewetting arable land in Lower Saxony and Bavaria compared to Schleswig-Holstein. The arable land on organic soils in Brandenburg is predominantly covered by crops

with low standard gross margins (rye, sunflowers, cultivated grassland), while the arable land of Mecklenburg-Western Pomerania is to a larger extent covered by wheat, potatoes, and rapeseed, which are arable crop types providing comparatively high standard gross margins.

The average long-term opportunity costs amount to 318 €/ha*a for Germany as a whole. The opportunity costs in Lower Saxony, Schleswig-Holstein, and Bavaria are more than twice as high as in Mecklenburg-Western Pomerania and Brandenburg.

Fig. 4 illustrates the distribution of SOC across counties and crop type categories, incorporating the upper and lower boundaries along with the corresponding standard deviations for the years 2021–2023. The analysis reveals that, influenced by factors such as the ongoing conflict in Ukraine, input shortages, and elevated output prices, the standard deviation of SOC—particularly for the upper and lower boundaries of cash crops—is notably high. In contrast, the standard deviation of the SOC for permanent grassland is comparatively moderate.

3.4. Total Agricultural Opportunity Costs

The immediate rewetting of all agriculturally used organic soils would incur total short-term opportunity costs of between €668 million and €2.1 billion (three-year average), depending on the degree of reducing in ruminant livestock. Annual long-term opportunity costs of about 355 million € are about half of the lower boundary of short-term opportunity costs and 20% of the upper boundary of short-term opportunity costs in Germany.

The highest total opportunity costs occur in Lower Saxony. In the short term, costs of between € 331 million and € 1221 million are incurred annually. This accounts for more than 50% of the total opportunity costs in Germany, even though only 39% of the organic soils used for agriculture are located in Lower Saxony, due to comparatively high gross margins. Unlike Lower Saxony, Brandenburg and Mecklenburg-Western Pomerania have significantly lower opportunity costs relative to their share of organic soils, reflecting lower gross margins as well as lower ruminant densities.

Fig. 5. Short-term opportunity costs (upper boundary and lower boundary) of rewetting organic soils in the counties across federal states. Source: Own illustration and calculations based on Dilger, Faulhaber (2006b); KTBL, (2023); KYNETEC, unpublished; Tegetmeyer et al. (2021); Neuenfeldt et al. (2024); Tetteh et al. (2024). Remark: crop type aggregation: productive agricultural areas incl. special crops.

Table 3
Opportunity costs of rewetting productive agriculturally used organic soils per ton of CO₂eq/ha*a.

	Short-term opportunity costs in €/ha*a		Long-term opportunity costs in €/ha*a	GHG mitigation potential in t CO ₂ eq/ha*a	Opportunity costs per ton of CO ₂ eq/ha*a in €/t CO ₂ eq		
	Lower bound	Upper bound			Short-term lower bound	Short-term upper bound	Long-term
Schleswig-Holstein	514	2567	356	28.6	18	90	12
Lower Saxony	741	2726	431	29.9	25	91	14
Bavaria	1021	2348	346	29.7	34	80	12
Brandenburg	263	674	146	28.6	9	24	5
Mecklenburg-Western Pomerania	289	813	190	27.4	11	30	7
Germany	598	1959	318	29.1	21	67	11

Source: Own calculations based on DESTATIS, (2021); Dilger, Faulhaber (2006b); KTBL, (2023); KYNETEC, unpublished; Tegetmeyer et al. (2021); Neuenfeldt et al. (2024); Tetteh et al. (2024). Remark: Average short-term opportunity costs (upper boundary) divided by GHG mitigation potential of arable land (34.9 t CO₂eq/ha*a) and permanent grassland (26.2 t CO₂eq/ha*a) weighted according to area share.

3.5. Regional differences

Differences in organic soil use and associated opportunity costs do not only occur between federal states but also at higher spatial resolutions. In Lower Saxony, for example, there is a (north-)west to southeast gradient in the proportion of organic soils in the total agricultural area as well as in the opportunity costs (Fig. 5). While organic soils account for 59–31% of the total agricultural area in the northwestern counties of Lower Saxony, there are almost no agriculturally used organic soils in

the southeastern counties. Organic soils in the Northwest are characterized by intensive dairy cow husbandry, resulting in average short-term opportunity costs (upper boundary) between 1692 and 3375 €/ha*a.

48 and 1111 €/ha*a. The cultivation of cereals, and especially potatoes, is an important form of organic soil use in the western counties of Lower Saxony (Grafschaft Bentheim, Emsland). Furthermore, calf and beef fattening are the dominant forms of ruminant husbandry dependent on forage from organic soils (Emsland, Cloppenburg). Accordingly,

Table 4
Average short-term opportunity costs of rewetting agriculturally used organic soils and compensating CAP second pillar interventions.

Federal State	Intervention	Subsidy rate	Short-term opportunity costs	
			Lower boundary	Upper boundary
Lower Saxony	Permanent grassland			
	Targeted minimal water table: 20 cm below surface, + Sustainable use of permanent grassland	536 €/ha + 453 €/ha = 989 €/ha	227 €/ha 972 €/ha	2604 €/ha 2428 €/ha
	Sum	+ 2569 €/ha		
	Arable land			
	Targeted minimal water table: 20 cm below surface, + Conversion of arable land to permanent grassland (7 years)	= 3105 €/ha		
	Sum			
	Permanent grassland			
	Targeted minimal water table: 20 cm below surface (12 years) + Sustainable use of permanent grassland	900 €/ha + 125 €/ha = 1025 €/ha	507 €/ha 1203 €/ha	2152 €/ha 2105 €/ha
	Sum	900 €/ha	1203 €/ha	2105 €/ha
	Arable land	3300 €/ha		
Cultivation of paludiculture (12 years) OR targeted minimal water table: 20 cm below surface (12 y) + Conversion of arable land to permanent grassland	= 2275 €/ha			
Sum (average over 12 years)				
Permanent grassland				
Brandenburg	Targeted minimal water table: 10 cm below surface	199 €/ha + 48 €/ha	118 €/ha 460 €/ha	533 €/ha 862 €/ha
	+ Targeted minimal water table in winter half-year: at surface	+ 165 €/ha = 412 €/ha		
	+ Sustainable use of permanent grassland	= 350 €/ha		
	Sum			
	Arable land			
	Cultivation of paludiculture			
	Sum			
	Permanent grassland	450 €/ha	136 €/ha	666 €/ha
	Targeted minimal water table: 10 cm below surface	+ 190 €/ha = 640 €/ha	937 €/ha	1431 €/ha
	+ Sustainable use of permanent grassland	450 €/ha + 450		
Mecklenburg-Western Pomerania	Permanent grassland			
	Targeted minimal water table: 10 cm below surface, + Sustainable use of permanent grassland	450 €/ha + 190 €/ha = 640 €/ha	937 €/ha	1431 €/ha
	Sum			
	Arable land			
	Cultivation of paludiculture			
	Sum			
	Permanent grassland	450 €/ha	136 €/ha	666 €/ha
	Targeted minimal water table: 10 cm below surface	+ 190 €/ha = 640 €/ha	937 €/ha	1431 €/ha
	+ Sustainable use of permanent grassland	450 €/ha + 450		
	Sum			

Table 4 (continued)

Federal State	Intervention	Subsidy rate	Short-term opportunity costs	
			Lower boundary	Upper boundary
	Sum	€/ha		
	Arable land	= 900		
	Targeted minimal water table: 10 cm below surface	€/ha 450 €/ha + 1300		
	+ Cultivation of paludiculture	€/ha = 1750€/ha		
	Sum			
	OR Targeted minimal water table: 10 cm below surface			
	+ Conversion of arable land to permanent grassland			
	Sum			

Source interventions: Own composition based on (BMEL, 2023; MKLLU MV, 2023b; Niedersächsisches MU, 2023; MLUK Brandenburg, 2023a; MLUK Brandenburg, 2023b; StMELF Bayern, 2023). Source opportunity costs: Own calculations, Remark: Crop type aggregations: permanent grassland, productive arable land excl. special crops.

short-term opportunity costs (upper boundary) are high (2182 – 3372 €/ha*a).

There is also a gradient in opportunity costs in Schleswig-Holstein (first map in Fig. 5) and Mecklenburg-Western Pomerania (second row middle in Fig. 5). In Schleswig-Holstein, the decreasing ruminant livestock density from west to east is the reason for lower short-term opportunity costs in the eastern counties of Schleswig-Holstein. In Mecklenburg-Western Pomerania, it is a shift in the dominant ruminant types: dairy cows dominate organic soil use in the western counties, while in the eastern counties, suckler cows dominate.

4. Discussion

4.1. Agricultural opportunity costs and other costs of rewetting in relation to GHG mitigation benefits

To contextualize the agricultural opportunity costs of rewetting organic soils, we relate them to the associated GHG mitigation potential given by Tiemeyer et al. (2020) and to GHG mitigation costs in other sectors. The European Union has established a European Emission Trading System (EU ETS), which limits GHG emissions from certain energy-intensive sectors (European Commission, 2016). In 2023, the average price of traded allowances under the EU-ETS was about 84 €/t CO2eq (UBA, 2024). Table 3 shows that the long-term as well as the lower bound of the short-term agricultural opportunity costs of rewetting in the federal states rich in organic soils are substantially below the EU ETS price. The upper bound of short-term mitigation costs is below the EU ETS price in most federal states and slightly above in Schleswig-Holstein and Lower Saxony.

In addition to agricultural opportunity costs, rewetting agriculturally used rewetted peatland would induce other costs:

- Schäfer et al. (2022b) estimate the initial engineering and planning costs based on completed projects, spanning approximately 30, 000 ha. They find a broad cost range, from 1065 Euro per hectare to 17,555 Euro per hectare and report an average cost of 4000 Euro per hectare. Assuming a payback period of 30 years and an interest rate of 3%, this amounts to 7 €/t CO2eq.
- Schäfer et al. (2022a) and Wichmann et al. (2022b) estimate the cost of implementing paludiculture at 10,000 €/ha on average. Assuming

Fig. 6. Grassland regionalization results: Upper maps: estimated yields for the relevant years at the county level; Lower Maps: SGM yields without regionalisation

a payback period of 30 years and an interest rate of 3%, this amounts to about 18 €/t CO₂e q.

- In addition, costs of 22 €/ha annually for monitoring, reporting, and verification (MRV) are reported by (Schäfer et al., 2022b), which is below 1 €/t CO₂e q.

This yields a range of average total GHG mitigation costs in Germany between 19 €/t CO₂e q in the long term and 75 €/t CO₂e q in the short-term (upper bound). In case of paludiculture being established, rewetting costs would be about 18 €/t CO₂e q higher, though revenues from paludiculture would potentially offset at least a part of the implementation and opportunity costs (Schäfer et al., 2022c).

Finally, the future opportunity cost of rewetting depends on changes in future framework conditions of agriculture in Germany. For example, the carbon price is expected to rise to 130–160 €/t CO₂e q by 2030 (Pahle et al., 2022), which would make rewetting in all federal states cost-efficient even if the short-term upper bound of opportunity costs as well as initial costs, MRV costs and the costs of establishing paludiculture are accounted for.

Furthermore, agricultural market conditions in the EU may change. This may be due to changes in world market prices for inputs and outputs, for which the EU market is integrated in international markets, but also due to changes in EU internal markets. For example, human consumption of animal products and thus derived demand for feed may change with a shift toward more plant-based diets, which would affect input and output prices for animal products as well as animal stocks,

potentially reducing opportunity costs of rewetting. Also, political conditions, such as the level of direct payments, can vary, influencing the opportunity cost of rewetting. Changes in environmental conditions, such as climate change, can also impact the cost-benefit analysis of rewetting. (Glenk et al., 2021) demonstrate that delaying restoration results in a substantial "opportunity cost of inaction." As global temperatures increase, the rate at which carbon is lost from drained peat accelerates. Additionally, the physical costs of rewetting are expected to rise as climate change progresses. Hotter, drier summers speed up peat subsidence and cracking, making hydrological restoration more technically challenging and costly.

4.2. Short-term opportunity costs and compensating CAP second pillar interventions

The comparison with GHG abatement costs of EU ETS companies highlights the economic efficiency of rewetting organic soils. Currently, though, there are almost no profitable wet land use alternatives. For a transitional period until wet value chains are established, governmental support for rewetting can initiate the process. In the latest revision of the CAP, the federal states of Lower Saxony (Niedersächsisches MU, 2023), Bavaria (StMELF Bayern, 2023), Brandenburg (MLUK Brandenburg, 2022a), and Mecklenburg-Western Pomerania (MKLLU MV, 2023b) have introduced interventions for peatland protection measures intended to economically incentivize the rewetting of organic soils by compensating for the opportunity costs incurred (EL-0101-03). To

assess the incentivizing effect of the interventions, the following section compares the subsidy rates with the average opportunity costs of rewetting (Table 4).

In Germany, the second pillar interventions of the CAP are designed at the federal state level. Accordingly, the required management commitments, the subsidy rates, and the ability to combine different interventions vary among the federal states (BMEL, 2023). All interventions related to organic soils require continued use. The minimum requirement is to cut the grown biomass once per year. Some federal states distinguish the subsidy rates of peatland protection measures according to the targeted water table. We focus on the highest possible target because we assume complete discontinuation of drained land use activities in our opportunity cost analysis. Where applicable, we take into account the combination of interventions for the rewetting of organic soils with interventions for the extensification of permanent grassland, since the rewetting of grassland necessarily comes at the expense of extensifying its use. Unless otherwise indicated, interventions have a commitment period of five years.

In **Lower Saxony**, the rewetting of organic soils is funded at 536 €/ha*a, provided that the minimal water table does not fall below a distance of 20 cm from the soil surface in winter and 40 cm in summer. When permanent grassland is rewetted, the intervention can be combined with an intervention for sustainable grassland use, provided that at least 0.3 roughage-consuming livestock units per hectare of grassland are kept. The combined subsidy rate amounts to 989 €/ha*a. This exceeds the lower bound of SOC for rewetting permanent grassland in the southeastern parts of Lower Saxony but not in the northern and western parts, where substantially higher short-term opportunity costs are incurred.

The conversion of arable land into permanent grassland is subsidized with 2569 €/ha*a over a period of seven years. The combination of this intervention with the interventions for permanent grassland would exceed the upper limit of SOC of rewetting arable land in all regions of Lower Saxony. The limiting aspect is the low funding volume for the intervention for peatland protection measures (BMEL, 2023).

Since 2024, **Bavaria** offers CAP second pillar interventions for peatland protection measures on permanent grassland (StMELF Bayern, 2023). The use of permanent grassland with minimal water tables of 20 cm below the soil surface is funded with 900 €/ha*a over a period of 12 years. If 0.3–1.0 livestock units per hectare of permanent grassland are kept at the farm level, the intervention can be combined with a premium for the sustainable use of permanent grassland. The total premium amounts to 1025 €/ha*a. This exceeds the lower bound of average SOC.

Additionally, Bavaria has introduced an intervention for planted paludiculture, which we assume will be implemented on arable land. A subsidy of 2200 €/ha*a, paid over a period of 12 years, is sufficient to compensate even for the upper boundary of average SOC. However, paludiculture is currently not a profitable land use alternative. Thus, the premium needs to cover potential initial losses of this land use form as well. Furthermore, the conversion of arable land into permanent grassland is funded with 3300 €/ha*a. Since the commitment period of this intervention is five years, the average premium over 12 years amounts to 2275 €/ha*a if combined with the premium for peatland protection measures on permanent grassland.

Brandenburg offers a maximum subsidy of 412 €/ha*a for the rewetting and extensive use of permanent grassland located on organic soils. This intervention requires a targeted minimal water level of 10 cm below the soil surface in summer and a water level at the soil surface in winter (MLUK Brandenburg, 2022a). In contrast to Lower Saxony and Bavaria, cutting and removing the growing biomass once per year is sufficient to fulfill the minimal usage requirements for sustainable grassland use (MLUK Brandenburg, 2023b). The subsidy rate almost covers the average upper bound short-term opportunity costs of rewetting permanent grassland in Brandenburg which amounts to 492 €/ha*a.

The use of rewetted arable land with planted paludiculture, in

contrast, is rather underfunded. A premium of 350 €/ha*a is at the lower boundary of average SOC of rewetting arable land. Hence, it would only incentivize rewetting if paludiculture is profitable and itself contributes to covering a portion of the SOC. Neither the intervention for paludiculture nor the intervention for the conversion of arable land to permanent grassland can be combined with peatland protection measures (MLUK Brandenburg, 2022c).

In **Mecklenburg-Western Pomerania**, the subsidy rate offered for a targeted water table of 10 cm below the soil surface in combination with the sustainable use of permanent grassland on organic soils amounts to 640 €/ha*a. This is about 200 € more than what is offered to the farmers in Brandenburg. A similar incentivizing effect can be expected, since the average SOC are also about 200 € above those in Brandenburg.

Furthermore, Mecklenburg-Western Pomerania offers a subsidy of 900 €/ha*a for the introduction of planted paludiculture at a targeted water table of 10 cm below the soil surface. This covers lower bound of the average SOC of rewetting arable land. Provided that the revenues from paludiculture at least cover its production costs, the subsidy has an incentivizing effect for farmers whose animal husbandry is not affected by rewetting. Alternatively, the intervention for converting arable land into permanent grassland can be combined with the intervention for peatland protection measures (MKLLU MV, 2023a). The total premium amounts to 1750 €/ha*a and overcompensates the opportunity costs.

All interventions compensate for at least the lower bound of SOC, with a few even compensating for the upper bound. However, the short duration of the interventions (7 years) results in a short planning horizon, which remains a major obstacle (Nordt et al., 2022), that only Bavaria addresses by extending its measures to 12 years. Another obstacle is the subsidies paid for the drainage-based use of organic soils, which we have not considered in our analysis. Regarding the first pillar interventions of the CAP, it could be argued that these payments will continue even after a field is rewetted and, therefore, have no impact on our results (Regulation EU, 2021/2115.). In contrast, second pillar interventions subsidizing sustainability measures on drained organic soils may not be continued in case of rewetting and therefore reduce the incentive effect of interventions for peatland protection measures.

In conclusion, the existing interventions can provide a real incentive for rewetting if the commitment period is extended, accompanied by sufficient programs to cover the initial costs of rewetting, and if counter-incentive subsidies are phased out. Additionally, funding for innovative land use alternatives, such as planted paludiculture, requires more political support.

4.3. Political implications

Rewetting is a de facto permanent land-use change, distinct, e.g., from crop rotation changes. Given that peatlands tend to be spatially clustered, the economic burden of rewetting falls unevenly, while the global social benefits, such as CO₂ mitigation, are dispersed (Glenk and Martin-Ortega, 2018). To reconcile societal climate goals with the realities faced by peatland farmers, a policy mix that combines reliable rewetting premiums for a period of 10–20 years with long-term perspectives for profitable wet use value chains is essential for farmers and land owners to agree to rewetting. The Common Agricultural Policy of the EU has made progress by including paludiculture as eligible and including rewetting as agro-environmental and climate measures in the second pillar, as well as eco-schemes in the first pillar. Yet, long-term reliability that matches the irreversibility of rewetting remains critical. Peat protection measures under the ANK provide the perspective of more long-term reliability, conditional on its extension beyond 2028.

In addition to public payments, market-based mechanisms such as private or public carbon certificates could provide revenue to peatland farmers. The EU Carbon Removal and Carbon Farming Certification Framework (CRCF) Regulation is an important step for quality assurance of tradable certificates. In the long run, the inclusion of emissions from peatlands in an EU-ETS system has a strong potential for incentivizing

rewetting, if designed appropriately (Agora Agriculture, 2024).

Finally, the rewetting of peatland does not only need financial incentives and the development of value chains for the wet use of peatlands, but also collective action. Rewetting needs the creation of new institutions, adjustments of the regulatory environment such as water laws, structured stakeholder processes and land consolidation processes (Grethe et al., 2021; Herold et al., 2025).

5. Conclusion and outlook

Our analysis provides an overview of the diverse agricultural use of organic soils in Germany. Differences can be observed between federal states and the counties and municipalities within federal states. Our land use analysis increases the accuracy of previous national organic soil use analyses because it captures differences in cultivation patterns at the field level. Nevertheless, uncertainties remain regarding the determination of ruminant livestock dependent on forage from organic soils.

A limitation of our analysis is that some data, for example, on rewetting costs beyond opportunity costs, stem from pilot projects. They provide valuable information, but scaling may result in over- or underestimation. Furthermore, the precise greenhouse gas (GHG) mitigation achieved through landscape-scale rewetting may differ from extrapolating data from localized measurements.

Based on our land use analysis, we have derived the opportunity costs of discontinuing drainage-based agricultural activities on organic soils when rewetting them. From an economy-wide economic efficiency perspective, it is advisable to rewet large parts of organic soils because the average costs per ton of carbon dioxide equivalent mitigated are below or at most around the GHG mitigation costs of other sectors, e.g., EU ETS industries, and far below the estimated economic welfare losses of €237 per ton of CO₂ emitted (UBA, 2023).

We provide a lower and an upper boundary of short-term opportunity costs. The range between both values is relatively wide. The range could be narrowed if the opportunities for adaptation especially for ruminant husbandry in case of rewetting are further investigated. As a first step, the relation between the proportion of organic soils in the total area farmed and the ability of farms to shift their production programs with the highest profitability to unaffected areas may be analyzed (Krimly et al., 2016).

While being efficient from an economy-wide perspective, governance approaches have to translate this into economic incentives for farmers and land owners on peatland. Until value chains for the wet use of peatlands are established and profitable, rewetting premiums are an important instrument to incentivize rewetting. Ideally, they should be

Appendix

1. Grassland intensities estimated at the regional level

To regionalize NUTS 2 regional permanent grassland yields to NUTS 3 regions, we employ, additionally to KTBL yield (KTBL, 2023) and quantity information at the NUTS 2 regional level, two supplementary datasets: remote-sensing-based field-level mowing event counts and total permanent grassland area.

Firstly, the mowing events dataset is generated from remote sensing (<https://zenodo.org/records/16941138>) and an algorithm that detects mowing events throughout the season.³ This field-level information is aggregated to the municipality level by calculating the median number of mowing events for all fields within a municipality. Subsequently, this data is further aggregated to the NUTS 3 regional level by calculating the average of the median number of mowing events.

Secondly, the total permanent grassland area is obtained from the the Thünen Agricultural Atlas at the NUTS 3 level (Neuenfeldt et al., 2024). It is used to determine the quantity produced in a NUTS 2 region.

The objective of this downscaling process is to vary permanent grassland yield at the NUTS 3 level based on the number of mowing events. Specifically, the higher the average number of median mowing events in a NUTS 3 region, the higher the permanent grassland yield in that region.

³ Schwieder, M., Wesemeyer, M., Frantz, D., Pfoch, K., Erasmi, S., Pickert, J., Nendel, C., & Hostert, P. (2022). Mapping grassland mowing events across Germany based on combined Sentinel-2 and Landsat 8 time series. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 269, 112795.

long-term, reliable and degressive (Agora Agriculture, 2026; Grethe et al., 2021).

Currently, rewetting premiums mainly exist under the CAP. It is still unclear to what extent farmers will accept the new programs. Our analysis shows that the planned compensation payments are often in the range between the lower and the upper bound of average short-term opportunity costs and sometimes even above the upper bound. However, providing financial compensation is often not enough to accept a program. Other factors, such as long-term reliability of the payments, legal aspects, and land owner structure, can hinder the success of these programs. These factors can lead to low uptake rates, as seen in the past for short-rotation coppice. In addition, area-based payments with premiums determined at the federal-state level are unlikely to reflect the heterogeneity of opportunity costs incurred in different regions of a federal state. They can lead to loss of effectiveness and generate windfall profits when predominantly the least productive organic soils, often characterized by comparatively high water tables, are rewetted.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Harald Grethe: Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Yang Xinxin:** Visualization, Validation, Software, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Tetteth Gideon Okpoti:** Writing – original draft, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Sebastian Neuenfeldt:** Validation, Software, Investigation, Data curation. **Alexander Gocht:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Conceptualization. **Niklas Domke:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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To achieve this, we define an objective function that minimizes the sum of squared deviations in yield between the NUTS 3 and NUTS 2 levels. The NUTS 2 yield serves as a reference and is scaled up or down based on the average number of median mowing events in each NUTS 3 region relative to the grand average of all mowing events in the NUTS 2 region. This scaling is further adjusted to account for variations in average median NUTS 3 mowing event numbers. The minimization process is subject to the constraint that the total quantity of permanent grassland in the NUTS 2 region remains unchanged after NUTS 3 yield adjustments. The objective function and the equality constraint are as follows:

$$\min_{x_r} \sum_r^R \left(\frac{(x_r - x_{obs} * \frac{mow_r}{mow_{mean}})}{mow_{sd}} \right)^2$$

$$s.t. q = \sum_r^R a_r * x_r$$

With r the NUTS 3 region of all R NUTS 3 regions in a NUTS 2 region, x_r is the variable yield at NUTS 3, x_{obs} is the observed yield at NUTS 2, mow_r being the NUTS 3 average median mowing event number, mow_{mean} and mow_{sd} being the mean and standard deviation of the average median mowing event numbers of all NUTS 3 regions in a NUTS 2 region. For the equality constraint, q is the NUTS 2 quantity of permanent grassland, and a_r is the NUTS 3 permanent grassland area. The distribution is shown in the following Fig. 6.

2. Calculation of the short- and long-term opportunity costs

This set of equations details the complete methodology used in the article to calculate both short-term (AvSOC) and long-term (AvLOC) opportunity costs of rewetting agriculturally used organic soils in Germany. The short-term calculations are particularly complex because they establish both a lower bound (assuming no livestock impact) and an upper bound (assuming livestock reduction is necessary), both of which are quantified using the Forage Refinement Value (FRV).

2.1 Short-Term Opportunity Cost (SOC)

Short-term opportunity costs represent the lost revenues minus variable costs (the Standard Gross Margin SGM) during the initial years after rewetting, when fixed costs cannot yet be eliminated.

Lower Cost Boundary

This calculates the AvSOC using the standard SGM, which represents the lower bound of costs because it assumes any loss of forage crop production does not impact livestock levels.

- Total SGM per Crop Type: This base step quantifies the overall profit loss for a specific crop (ct) in a county (c) using its area (Atot) and its SGM.

$$Atot_{ct,c} \cdot SGM_{ct,c} = SGMtot_{ct,c} \tag{1}$$

- Averaging AvSOC for Different Land Categories: The total SGM lost (Equation 15) is summed across different groupings and divided by the total area to get the AvSOC per hectare ($\frac{\sum SGMtot_{ct,c}}{\sum Atot_{ct,c}}$) for these categories:

- Total Productive Area (Incl. Special Crops): AvSOCprod_c
- Total Productive Area (Excl. Special Crops): AvSOCprodex_c
- Productive Arable Land (Excl. Special Crops): AvSOCprodarab_c
- Permanent Grassland: AvSOCperm_c

Upper Cost Boundary

The upper cost boundary uses the Forage Refinement Value (FRV) (calculated in Equations 6-8, see below) as the opportunity cost for forage areas. This FRV represents the loss of revenue from livestock that must be reduced due to forage shortage.

- AvSOC with FRV: Total Productive Area (Excl. Special Crops): This formula uses standard SGM for cash crops ($\sum SGMtot_{ct,c}$) and the FRV for forage crops ($\sum (Atot_{fct,c} \cdot FRV_{fct,c})$), dividing by the total area to get the upper-bound cost (AvSOCFRVprodex).

$$\frac{\sum_{ct} SGMtot_{ct,c} + \sum_{fct} (Atot_{fct,c} \cdot FRV_{fct,c})}{\sum_{ct} Atot_{ct,c} + \sum_{fct} Atot_{fct,c}} = AvSOCFRVprodex_c \tag{2}$$

- AvSOC with FRV: Productive Arable Land (Excl. Special Crops): This calculates the upper-bound AvSOC (AvSOCFRVprodarab) specifically for arable land, using the FRV for arable forage crops ($fct \in \{\text{cultivated grassland, silage maize}\}$).

$$\frac{\sum_{ct} SGMtot_{ct,c} + \sum_{fct} (Atot_{fct,c} \cdot FRV_{fct,c})}{\sum_{ct} Atot_{ct,c} + \sum_{fct} Atot_{fct,c}} = AvSOCFRVprodarab_c \tag{3}$$

- AvSOC with FRV: Permanent Grassland: The opportunity cost for permanent grassland (AvSOCFRVperm) is equal to its calculated FRV_{fct,c}.

$$FRV_{fct,c} = AvSOCFRV_{perm,c} \quad (4)$$

2.2 Long-Term Opportunity Cost (LOC)

The long-term opportunity costs (AvLOC) are assumed to be represented by the loss of ground rent, which is proxied by the current Tenure Fee (TF), as this rent would decline to zero if the soil were rewetted.

$$\sum_{luc} (TF_{luc,fs} \cdot \frac{A_{tot_{luc,fs}}}{A_{prod_{fs}}}) = AvLOC_{fs} \quad (5)$$

The formula calculates a weighted average of the tenure fees ($TF_{luc,fs}$) for different land use categories (luc) based on their area share ($\frac{A_{tot_{luc,fs}}}{A_{prod_{fs}}}$) of the productive organic soils in the federal state (fs), accurately reflect the lost ground rent when the land is rewetted, representing the permanent long-term loss of profitability.

These three Eqs. (6), (7), and (8) calculate the Forage Refinement Value (FRV), which represents the upper bound of the short-term opportunity costs (SOC) of rewetting forage areas.

The FRV is based on the critical assumption that a loss of forage area requires a proportional reduction in ruminant livestock due to forage shortages. Because local roughage markets are typically limited, the income loss is measured not by the selling price of the forage but by the lost profits from the animals the forage supported.

2.3 Calculation of the Forage Refinement Value (FRV)

The calculation quantifies the lost profitability of animal husbandry (SGM) and distributes it across the forage area that sustained it.

Eq. (6) determines the total annual Standard Gross Margin (SGM) that would be lost by abandoning a specific forage crop type (fct) within a county (c).

$$\sum_{rt} (X_{tot_{rt,fct,c}} \cdot SGM_{rt,c}) = SGM_{tot_{fct,c}} \quad (6)$$

$X_{tot_{rt,fct,c}}$: Total number of ruminants of type rt fed with forage crop type fct in the county c .

$SGM_{rt,c}$: Standard gross margin per animal of ruminant type rt in the county c .

$SGM_{tot_{fct,c}}$: Total SGM generated by feeding forage crop type fct in the county c .

Eq. (7) calculates the FRV per hectare for that specific forage crop type (fct) by normalizing the total lost profit by the area used.

$$\frac{SGM_{tot_{fct,c}}}{A_{tot_{fct,c}}} = FRV_{fct,c} \quad (7)$$

$SGM_{tot_{fct,c}}$: Total SGM generated by feeding forage crop type fct in county c .

$A_{tot_{fct,c}}$: Total area of forage crop type fct in county c .

$FRV_{fct,c}$: Forage refinement value of forage crop type fct in county c .

Eq. (8) calculates the overall average FRV per hectare for the county (c) across all relevant forage crop types (fct).

$$\frac{\sum_{fct} SGM_{tot_{fct,c}}}{\sum_{fct} A_{tot_{fct,c}}} = FRV_c \quad (8)$$

$\sum_{fct} SGM_{tot_{fct,c}}$: Sum of total SGM generated by all forage crop types in the county c .

$\sum_{fct} A_{tot_{fct,c}}$: Sum of total area of all forage crop types in the county c .

FRV_c : Average forage refinement value in the county c .

This FRV then serves as the SGM value (opportunity cost) for that hectare of forage land, reflecting the maximum loss the farm could incur if the land were rewetted and the dependent livestock had to be reduced. It typically represents a higher cost (the upper boundary) compared to valuing the forage simply as surplus feed (the lower boundary).

Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.landusepol.2026.108050](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2026.108050).

Data availability

We share all data and script upon request.

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